

THE NOTION OF FAMILY HONOUR IN SPOKEN AND WRITTEN ENGLISH

Axmedjanova Dilraxon Asatullayevna

teacher of the integrated English course N3, UzSWLU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6327512>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17th February 2022

Accepted: 22th February 2022

Online: 27th February 2022

KEY WORDS

honour, family, written English, spoken English, Family honour,

ABSTRACT

This article is about family honour in English and its role and importance in spoken and written language. Protecting the family and family honour, passing it on to the next generation, and its role in literature and the concept of honour, which is explored theoretically, with references to the most prominent researchers in the field, as well as historically, in order to reveal the concept's main transformations in English culture. In addition, the article gives a short introduction to the rest of the articles in the book.

Introduction: The terminology related to honor or family honor (or honour) is an abstract concept involving the perceived quality of worthiness and respectability that affects the social standing and the self-evaluation of a group of related people, both corporately and individually. The ideology and practice of family honor varies from country to country. Family honor is the feeling of pride a person has for their own family or clan, whether because of a unique family history, the achievements of ancestors, the elevated social status of their family, or because of some cultural aspect of their homeland that places a strong emphasis on associating personal identity.

In *Romeo and Juliet*, Shakespeare presents two families to the audience: the Montagues and the Capulets. These two families, despite their similarities, despise each other and continually battle. The conflict between the two families is almost

presented to be natural until Romeo Montague and Juliet Capulet fall in love.

It is here that everything changes. When Romeo and Juliet die, both families apologise for their behaviour and vow to honour each other, thus remembering their children's unjust deaths. Within the families, there are relationships which contribute to Romeo and Juliet's tragic deaths.

Shakespeare presents the similarities between the two families in the prologue, as he highlights to the audience how they are similar. E.g. "Two house holds, both alike in dignity." This shows that the two families are similar. The use of the word "dignity" highlight show the families have similar principle and status in the city of Verona.

In the opening scene, Shakespeare presents the families' servants fighting against each other, for their house's honour. The families themselves quickly get

involved and it turns into a fight against each other. "By the old Capulet, and Montague, have thrice disturbed the quiet of our streets." This shows the Prince's anger as Capulet and Montague have been involved in another fray on the streets of Verona, upsetting the peace. The families have "thrice disturbed the quiet of four streets" illustrating how the conflict is continuous and despite the Prince's warnings, they still continue to battle against each other.

When the families discover Romeo and Juliet have committed suicide, they apologise for their behaviour and vow to uphold their memory in their hearts. "O brother Montague, give me thy hand." This shows that Capulet wishes Montague to forgive him for their previous arguments. Capulet's address of Montague as "brother" illustrates how he wants their relationship to move forward; they are like brothers due to their deceased children's marriage.

Romeo and Juliet was set during a time of religious and political turmoil. Europe was a traditionally Catholic society with a strong belief in damnation for mortal sin. Suicide and bigamy were both considered to be mortal sins. Shakespeare was writing following 'The Reformation' and this was when England became a Protestant nation, having broken away from the control of the Catholic Church

Courtly love (like royalty) should be polite, ceremonious, restrained, intellectual, courteous and those involved should be in love with the idea of being in love. There was no contact, just an exchange of gifts, letters and poems. Divorce was impossible. Family honour was important to the Elizabethans. There was a strong belief that the slightest wrong or insults

must be avenged as a matter of personal pride or to protect reputation.

The theatre was a popular source of entertainment in Elizabethan England. Audiences included servants, labourers, the wealthy and they could become quite rowdy during performances. The poorer people in the audience stood on front of the stage and the more wealthy people sat in the covered galleries above. It was illegal for women to act, so female roles were played by young boys.

The father was the head of the household in this patriarchal society. Women had no rights or authority in law: they could not own property or money but could influence their husbands. Children were regarded as property and could be given in marriage to a suitable partner. This was often a political or financial transaction to secure and retain wealth. It was not unusual to be married very young. In high society, children were often raised by a 'wet nurse' and did not have a strong bond with their parents.

Family honor can be dependent upon many factors and areas that are affected by family honor include multiple aspects of lifestyle such as social status, religion, clothing, eating, education, job or career, ownership such as real estate, and marriage. People who live in cultures of honor, perceive family as the central institution in their society and a person's social identity depends largely on their family. Therefore, it is important for these individuals to fulfill expectations of family and society in order to be accepted by their family and experience feelings of belonging to this central institution that they are tied to through birth or marriage. In some cultures, maintaining family honor is perceived as more important than either

individual freedom, or individual achievement. The ideology and practice of family honor varies from country to country. Individuals of certain cultures are often unaware or discerning in their understanding of differing cultural traditions. Many fail to grasp the concept of honor as the basis for traditions such as defending one's honor or their family's. Some cultures value family honor more than others. Many times a family's honor may overpower the actions or beliefs of the individual. However, a theme that is common within many traditions is the respecting of elders. Children of the family are to respect their elders who have earned what some call a "badge of 'honor'" representative of their age. Once an individual has lived throughout life for several years, they have earned this badge of honor and should be shown respect teaching their young the cultural traditions that have deemed them honorable.

The honor of the family is usually called the whole system, which includes ideals, nobility, courage in the face of difficulties and trials. The choice of priority values and ideals characterize honest and dishonest. In a house where the honor of the family is honored, the culture of communication is observed, the mother land is treated with love, in any situation they maintain calm dignity, honesty is the absolute norm. A noble and honest family is characterized by a respectful attitude towards one's neighbor, mutual assistance. The main thing in it is that family does not accept vulgarity. In an honest family, prudence, discipline, self-

control are formed. Also in it is the formation of an honest and respectable personality. Strength coupled with courage is important for such a family. After all, it will be required in order not to be afraid to resist the wrong attitudes in society, reflect evil and be firm. A family that does not care about its own dignity and good name cannot be considered a model of nobility and moral purity. In such a cell of society, a place appears for disrespect for one's neighbor, lack of tact, aggressive mood and other.

A family with a complete lack of honor does not pursue justice. Its main features are parasitism and consumerism, burdened with unhealthy egoism. Morality and patriotic feelings, like faith, are ridiculed with contempt.

In a morally healthy and prosperous society, one can see the desire to preserve the family. And a respectable family man can be safely called a worthy citizen of his native country. The Orthodox Church teaches to strengthen the family as a whole. The powerful authority of the father and the sensitive care of them other teaches children to respect tradition and live righteously. Mutual love between husband and wife, strong family ties, the readiness of each to lay down his head for the prosperity of the Fatherland - these are the main signs of family honor. It is regrettable to talk about it, but in the modern world the concept of honor is dying, people are losing their bearings. But it is always worth remembering that only a nascent family can be built on the basis of faith, hope and love. Only in this lies happiness.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/zg6psbk/revision/4>

2. <https://www.definitions.net/definition/family+honor>
3. <https://lit.ukrtvory.ru/ustarelo-li-segodnya-ponyatie-chest-semi/>
4. Ginat J, Khazanov A, Eds. Changing nomads in a changing world. Brighton, UK: Sussex Academic Press 1998.
5. Taylor C. The politics of recognition, in Rav-tarbutiyut be-mivhanha-Yisreeliyut, Ed. OhadNa tomi. Jerusalem: Magnes 2003.
6. Marx E. The social context of violent behavior: a social anthropological study in an Israeli immigrant town. London: Routledge 2004; p.10.